

Table 1: Mice and human mutant DNA glycosylase phenotypes

DNA Glycosylase	Knock-out (ko) mice	Disease
UNG2	U residues accumulation; B-cell lymphomas	Defective CSR and SHM
SMUG1	Viable up to 1 year; <i>smug1 ung msh2</i> triple ko: lymphoid tumors	-
TDG	Embryonic lethal	-
MBD4	elevated C>T mutation frequency at CpG sites; in <i>apc</i> +/- mice: gastrointestinal cancer	-
NTHL1	Viable and healthy	Adenomatous polyposis and colorectal cancer
OGG1	Viable and healthy, 8-oxoG accumulation, moderate increase of spontaneous mutation frequency; age-dependent CAG expansion in mouse models of HD ; obese phenotype under high-fat diet	-
MUTYH	Intestinal tumors; <i>myh ogg1</i> double knock- out: lung and ovarian cancers and lymphomas; alteration of behavior and cognition	Multiple colon polyps and colorectal cancers
NEIL1	Metabolic syndrome; slight increase of lung adenomas and hepatocarcinomas in aged animals; <i>neil1 nthl1</i> double ko: increased cancer incidence	-
NEIL2	Genomic instability but not tumor formation, innate inflammation	-
NEIL3	Impairment of differentiation of neural progenitor cells in aged animals; learning and memory deficits; <i>apoe neil3</i> double ko: increased atherosclerosis under high-fat diet	-
MPG	Enhanced susceptibility to inflammation-associated colon cancer; alkylation-induced retinal degeneration	-

Lori 11/22/y 12:05 PM
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